

The Transition of Post-New Order as a Pattern of the Political System in Indonesia

Jan Mealino Ekklesia¹

Abstract

The change in the pattern of the political system in Indonesia is inseparable from the development of democratization and the political turmoil that engulfed it. the most significant change is the shift of authoritarian systems to more democratic systems. This paper will explain the causes of the Reformation Era and their impact on the relationship between the executive and legislative, the relationship between central and local governments, and the democratic process in the region.

Keywords: *New Order, Reformasi, Political System*

¹ Undergraduate students majoring in Sociology, Universitas Airlangga
Email : janmealino@gmail.com

Introduction : The Success of the Reformation Movement Changed the Pattern of the Political System in Indonesia

The transition of the system of government in Indonesia has changed since the beginning of independence. The transition of this system of government is accompanied by the change and development of democracy, bureaucratic system, and political culture. Uniquely, the period of Pancasila democracy (1965-1998), which greatly accentuated the presidential system and the re-inauguration of Pancasila and the Constitution as a formal foundation, in no way reflects the democratic system of government. The so-called Pancasila democracy (New Order) was precisely known as the authoritarian political system under Suharto (Haris, 2014). There are several phenomena that led to the Suharto-era political system being referred to as an authoritarian political system.

1. The president can be juridically elected several times. Suharto's leadership lasted for seven periods (1966-1997) indicating a subjective interpretation process in the constitution article by the regime (Haris, 2014, p. 1)
2. Restrictions on political parties of election participants. In the New Order era, only three political parties were allowed to participate in elections. Among others, the Golongan Karya (Golkar) faction is referred to as the "government party", the Perjuangan Demokrasi Indonesia (PDI), and the Partai Persatuan Pembangunan (PPP). Parties outside Golkar are a fusion of Islamist, nationalist, Christian, and other smaller parties. The reduction system of these parties will exacerbate the increasingly absolute control of power. Because, no more opposition political parties and other political forces are able to check and balances and power is very heavy on the executive (executive-heavy) than the legislative heavy (Purwoko, 2013, p. 6)
3. Restrictions on press freedom. The threat of a shake-up and freeze for print media across the government. The policy mechanism of SIUPP (Surat Izin Usaha Penerbitan Pers) is not separated from government hegemony. The government not only controls the production system but also controls and controls ideological institutions, such as culture, religion, education, and mass media (Eklöf, 2003, pp. 9-10).

4. The conduct of manipulative, intimidated, and repressive elections conducted on Suharto's regime (Haris, 2014, p. 3) (Budiardjo, 2012, pp. 132-133). Although the government implements a democratic mechanism that is Elections, but the essence of elections is not executed. Furthermore, in accordance with the statement by Lord Acton "*Power tends to corrupt and absolute power corrupts absolutely*" (Acton-Creighton Correspondence, 1887, p. 9). Abuse of power, in addition to damaging good governance units, will exacerbate the practice of corruption, collusion and nepotism.
5. The concept of Dwifungsi ABRI which is officially recognized as part of the socio-political system in addition to carrying out its function as a defense of the state (military force & social-political force) (Crouch, 2007, pp. 22-23) (Kuncoro, 2013, p. 356). Military intervention in civilian affairs indirectly threatens the purity of democracy. Because with military access to the socio-political system, military power is increasingly unstoppable (superior). Many of the military members sit in executive positions such as camat, minister, governor, regent and mayor (Haris, 2014, p. 4).

Based on the five phenomena above, it can be concluded that the pattern of authoritarianism adopted during the reign of the New Order did not side with the interests of the people. So in 1997/8, there was a massive change in the political system in Indonesia. Students at that time received support from community leaders and government officials to jointly demand reforms, including the overthrow of Suharto's leadership. The strong reason for Suharto's overthrow was due to the diminished executive power and strengthening legislative powers, as well as the economic crisis that engulfed Indonesia. The New Order suffered a rift economically and politically. This will result in a prone split among the elite, namely a rapid and unplanned change of power (Marijan, 2011, pp. 2-14). Not only that, the influence of civil society forces from intellectuals and students to make Indonesia more democratic into resistance movements against the New Order (Marijan, 2011, p. 5)

The success of the Reformation system changed the New Order system in power for more than thirty years, among others:

1. Related to the economic crisis

The decline and destruction of the New Order regime began with the monetary crisis that hit Asia in 1997/8. The growth and development established by the New Order since 1967 does not bring complete and fair prosperity to the People of Indonesia (Suwirta, 1998). Later, the economic crisis that engulfed Indonesia made the regime's control powerless, the emergence of tensions between the government and the industrial and economic sectors, as well as a setback to the legitimacy of the regime.

2. Related to political mobilization

The mobilization of people's politics is strongly related to military and authoritarian regimes (Perlmutter, 1980), where political mobilization serves to support electoral activities and regime interests (Nugroho, 2011). But as industrialization and the middle class and modernization emerged questions were "critical" of the ruling regime. Thus, the mobilization that was once formed to support the regime now contains opposition and challenges to the existing regime.

3. Related to international pressures

Repression and international repression were also the reason for the overthrow of the New Order regime. For example, in October 1997, Suharto was forced to borrow funds to the International Monetary Fund (IMF) in order to break the circle of economic destruction and restore government trust (O'Rourke, 2002, pp. 44-46). The IMF also had a specific goal of demanding a series of radical reforms before providing a \$43 billion loan (O'Rourke, 2002)

4. Related to the breakup of the regime

The destruction of the regime can be caused by internal regime rifts. The rift can be caused by institutional structure, where regime dominance results in decisions that cause disappointment to its supporters (Marijan, 2011)

The Implications of Changing the Pattern of the Political System in Indonesia on the Electoral System, Party, Regional Autonomy, and Democratization in the Region

The process of changing the political system from the New Order to reform brought the result of a change of government institutions, namely the resignation of President Suharto on 21 May 1998 and replaced by B.J. Habibie (Marijan, 2011). The next movement is the creation of laws and amendments to the Constitution that further open up the democratization and accountability of the system of government (Marijan, 2011). There are five implications for changing the pattern of the New Order political system to the Reform Order:

A. Changes to the electoral system and changes to the party system

Elections in Indonesia before and after the New Order adopted a system of proportionality, as the proportional system co-ed the multiparty system and even accommodated smaller parties (Marijan, 2011, p. 91). Meanwhile, the proportional system underwent modifications after the New Order including: a semi-open list proportional system, the selection of parties and candidates within the party, the allocation of party seats from the sequence number to the most votes, as well as direct elections of the President and Vice President (Marijan, 2011, p. 108)

According to Robert Huckshorn (in (White, 2006, p. 5)) political parties are autonomous groups consisting of citizens, whose function is to gain control and power of government by elections. So, elections are the path of political parties gaining power. Significant changes from the New Order to reform include: reusable multiparty system, no dominant party government, parliamentary threshold increased to 4% at the 2019 General Election, and the tightening of election requirements as a form of simplification of the party system (Marijan, 2011) (Suwarko, 2013)

B. Changes in the political representation system

Representation is a form of modern democracy. In modern society, political processes must be represented given the diverse number of communities, the wide scope of the region, and complex technical issues (Marijan, 2011). Meanwhile, the concept of representation is carried out through representative institutions such as DPR/D and DPD. Changes in the political representation system of the New Order to the Reform era as

follows: strengthening the institutions of the DPR/D and DPD so that the check and balances mechanism becomes strong, changes in the position of the DPRD to the regional head by incorporating legislative powers in the region, enacted a bicameral system, as well as the concentration of female and marginal representatives (UU No.10 tahun 2008 on the representation of women amounted to 30% of the total members of political parties). However, representation is only an aspect of participation so it is often represented only as an accessory and formality only (Phillip, 1995)

C. Relations between the central government and local governments (Regional Autonomy and Decentralization) and Democratization in the region

The discussion of decentralization is not separated from autonomy in carrying out duties (Wahyudi & Zakiyah, 2020, p. 7). Decentralization has three perspectives, namely political, administrative and economic perspectives (Marijan, 2011). Decentralization and implementation of Regional Autonomy in the New Order is very limited, i.e. only on administrative decentralization. Post-New Order decentralization is broader, encompassing political and fiscal decentralization. More, changes to Regional Autonomy and decentralization can be written as follows:

- a. The enactment of Law No. 22 of 1999, Law No. 32 of 2004, and Law No. 23 of 2014 concerning Local Government, as well as Law No. 25 of 1999 and Law No. 32 of 2004 regarding the Financial Balance between the Central and Local Governments, has resulted in provincial and regency/city governments gaining more extensive autonomy in managing natural resources and human resources.
- b. By strengthening decentralization policies, the process of public services is more efficient and the creation of a government that has responsibility, accountability, and encouraged democratization in the region (Marijan, 2011, pp. 150-151).
- c. Strengthening decentralization and regional autonomy will encourage the realization of check and balances in power as well as the opportunity for the emergence of local political parties. It should all be supported by other policies such as the improvement of the political party system and the electoral system (Marijan, 2011, p. 167)

In the meantime, According to Smith, democracy in the region as proof of democracy at the center (Smith, 1998, pp. 85-87). There are 4 reasons to reinforce his statement. First, talking

about democratization in the region means talking also about political education events that are relevant to citizens (*free societies*). Second, local government as a tool of central government control. Third, democracy in the region is considered capable of fostering political participation rather than in the center. Fourth, the Case of Colombia shows that the legitimacy of local government will strengthen the central government (Smith, 1998). In addition, the process of accelerating the democratic transition in the region not only revolves around political distribution (decentralization) but also related to economic distribution.

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